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Assessment of Natural Radioactivity Content and Estimation of Radiation Hazards in soil Samples of Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The levels of natural radioactive elements in the soil at Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, were measured to assess potential radiation exposure and associated health risks to the local population. A 3" x 3" NaI(Tl) gamma-ray detector was used for the measurements. The findings revealed average activity concentrations of 14.99 ± 0.98 Bqkg⁻¹ for ²²⁶Ra, 9.67 ± 0.76 for ²³²Th and 394.24 ± 10.19 Bqkg⁻¹ for ⁴⁰K. The radium equivalent activity was found to be 59.17 ± 2.85 Bqkg⁻¹. Computed mean value for gamma dose rate for the soil samples was 29.21 nGy h⁻¹, with consequent average annual effective dose equivalent of 0.04 mSv/year. All these values, along with other radiation hazard parameters, were well within the safety limits established by the United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation. Therefore, radiation exposure in the area poses no significant risks to the students and residents of the Polytechnic. Statistical analysis of the results showed that ²²⁶Ra is the principal contributor to internal exposure to gamma radiation among the population. Results of this study provide a fundamental radiation data baseline for further radiological studies in the region.

Keywords: Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic, soil, NaI(Tl) detector, gamma dose rate, Birnin-kebbi, Nigeria

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Human exposure to ionizing radiation is a constant and unavoidable part of life on Earth (Mbonu&Ben,2021; Pemmaraju *et al.*,2023). Ionizing radiation comes from natural sources like primordial radionuclides that formed when the Earth was created, as well as from cosmic rays interacting with the atmosphere (cosmogenic radionuclides). Additionally, human activities such as nuclear testing, coal burning, nuclear power plants, fertilizer use, spacecraft launches, and medical treatments can create

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artificial radionuclides (Muhammad *et al.*, 2024; Tarbool *et al.*, 2022). Terrestrial radiation, for instance, comes from radioactive elements that naturally occur in soils, rocks, water, building materials, and the air (Khandaker *et al.*, 2025; Srinivasa *et al.*, 2024). Some of these radionuclides enter the human body through the food chain or by inhalation. Humans are exposed to a certain level of ionizing radiation daily, with about 87% of this exposure coming from natural sources, particularly from uranium-238 (^{238}U), thorium-232 (^{232}Th), and potassium-40 (^{40}K) (UNSCEAR, 2008). These radionuclides which constitutes major radionuclides of environmental concern are the principal contributors to background radiation and total effective radiation dose received by the human population (Rahman *et al.*, 2018; Ugbede *et al.*, 2021). These naturally occurring radioactive elements are the main contributors to background radiation and the total effective radiation dose humans receive. Radioactive elements are found in all geological formations, including rocks and soil, with their concentrations determined by local geographical and geological conditions (Cherie & Deressu, 2023; Echeweozo *et al.*, 2024). Soil which serves as major reservoir for these radionuclides, is the primary source of constant radiation exposure to man. Soil, which acts as a key reservoir for these radionuclides, is the main source of on-going radiation exposure to humans. It also facilitates the movement of these radionuclides throughout the environment being leached into surface water, entering groundwater, released into the atmosphere, or absorbed by plants through their roots. As such, soil is an essential medium for evaluating radiological health risks and radiation contamination. While natural radiation is an inherent part of our environment, human activities have significantly altered the spread of naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM), sometimes leading to levels that can be harmful to human health (Aguko *et al.*, 2020).

Radiation exposure has been linked to various health problems, most notably cancer, with lung cancer being the most recognized due to indoor radon exposure (Dina *et al.*, 2022; Missimer *et al.*, 2019; Muhammad *et al.*, 2024). Despite the fact that cancer is a major public health concern and efforts are being made to promote regular testing and early treatment, radiation exposure from terrestrial radionuclides is not often addressed in many developing countries. This lack of focus is likely due to a scarcity of information regarding radiation levels in these areas. Therefore, measuring soil radioactivity is crucial for understanding any changes in environmental radiation and assessing the risks posed to surrounding populations according to international safety guidelines. While databases on soil radioactivity are gradually being built in many countries, there is limited data on the natural radiation levels at Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic (WUFP) in Birnin Kebbi. This study aims to fill that gap by providing a detailed analysis of the activity levels of terrestrial radionuclides on the WUFP campus and evaluating the associated radiation risks for staff, students, and the general public.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Sample Collection and Preparation

Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic (WUFP) is situated in Birnin Kebbi, the capital city of Kebbi State in northwestern Nigeria. Geographically, it lies between latitudes $12^{\circ}27.454'\text{N}$ and $12^{\circ}28.239'\text{N}$, and longitudes $004^{\circ}13.624'\text{E}$ and $004^{\circ}14.874'\text{E}$. The institution was established in 1977 and currently has an estimated student population of around 6,000.

To create a baseline record of the radiation levels across the WUFP campus, a total of (99) surface soil samples were collected. These samples were taken from the top 5 to 10 centimetres of undisturbed soil using a hand trowel and a digger. The entire campus was covered during the sampling process. Details of the sampling locations, number of samples collected from each area, and the corresponding sample codes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Sample collection points and sample codes

Sample site	Sample ID	No of Samples
Art and Social Sciences	ASS	5
Survey	SVY	4
Business Dept	BSD	4
Lab Science	LBS	5
Female hostel	FLH	4
Estate management	EST	4
Administrative block	ADB	5
Quantity survey	QTS	4
Student Affairs	STA	5
Staff quarters	STQ	4
Architecture	ARC	5
NCE	NCE	5
Engineering	ENG	5
Mosque	MSQ	5
Computer science	CPT	5
Male hostel	MLH	5
Urban and Reg. planning	URP	5
Building	BLD	5
Accounts dept	ACC	5
Clinic	CLC	5
ICT	ICT	5

After collection, the soil samples were carefully cleaned to remove any organic material, stones, or other unwanted debris. Each sample was then placed in a properly labeled, sealed polyethylene bag to avoid contamination and safely transported to the laboratory for further processing.

In the lab, the samples were left open to air-dry at room temperature for approximately 48 hours to eliminate any moisture. This drying step is important because, as noted by the IAEA (2003), moisture can interfere with accurate radiation measurements. Once dry, the soil was ground into a fine powder using a mortar and pestle, then passed through a 2mm mesh sieve to ensure uniformity. The resulting fine, consistent samples were placed in labeled containers, tightly sealed, and stored for about 42 days. This waiting period allows for radioactive equilibrium to be reached between the parent radionuclides and their decay products, as recommended by (Agbalagba & Onoja, 2011; Hussein, 2019).

2.2 Instrumentation Sample Analysis

The gamma spectrometry system used for analyzing the soil samples included a 3" x 3" sodium iodide detector doped with thallium NaI(Tl), manufactured by Princeton Gamma Tech, USA. To minimize interference from surrounding background radiation, the detector was enclosed in a cylindrical lead shield. It was connected to a Gamma Spectacular multichannel analyzer (model GS-2000 Pro), which was in turn linked to a computer for visualizing and analyzing the gamma-ray spectra using Thermano software.

To ensure accurate identification and measurement of radionuclides, the system was calibrated both for energy and efficiency. Energy calibration was performed using an RSS8 gamma source set, traceable to Spectrum Techniques LLC, USA. This involved recording spectra from gamma-emitting point sources with known energy values. Efficiency calibration was carried out using a reference source with known levels of radioactive material to determine the detector's response to different radionuclides.

Before measuring the actual soil samples, an empty container was counted for 18,000 seconds to determine the background radiation level. After the sealed soil samples had reached secular equilibrium (a balanced state between parent and daughter radionuclides), each was placed on the detector and measured for the same 18,000-second duration.

Specific gamma-ray energies (photopeaks) were analyzed to identify the radionuclides present. For ²²⁶Ra, the peaks at 295.3 keV (²¹⁴Pb) and 1764.5 keV (²¹⁴Bi) were used. For ²³²Th, peaks at 238.6 keV (²¹²Pb), 911.1 keV (²²⁸Ac), and 2614.7 keV (²⁰⁸Tl) were analyzed. For ⁴⁰K, the characteristic peak at 1460.0 keV was used. The activity concentration A (Bq kg⁻¹) of each radionuclide in the sample was calculated using the following formula: (Alotaibi *et al.*, 2024; Ibraheem *et al.*, 2018):

$$A = \frac{C_{net}}{P_{\gamma} \times \epsilon \times m \times t} \quad (1)$$

In the equation used to calculate activity concentration C_{net} represents the net count of the gamma-ray peak for each radionuclide, obtained by subtracting the background count from the gross count, P_γ is the absolute gamma-ray emission probability for the specific radionuclide, ε denotes the full-energy peak efficiency of the detector at the corresponding energy, m is the mass of the sample (in kilograms), and t is the counting time (in seconds). To assess the sensitivity of the measurement system, the Minimum Detectable Activity (MDA) for each radionuclide was determined using equation 2:

$$MDA = \frac{2.71 + 4.66 (\sigma)}{P_{\gamma} \times \epsilon \times m \times t} \quad (2)$$

where σ is the standard deviation of the background count within the energy range of interest, measured over the same counting duration t. The MDA for the radionuclides of interest are 2.58 Bq kg⁻¹, 1.05 Bq kg⁻¹ and 9.86 Bq kg⁻¹, for ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K respectively.

2.3 Evaluation of Radiological dose and risk Parameters

2.3.1 Radium equivalent activity (Ra_{eq})

Is a widely used radiological index that provides a single value to represent the gamma radiation hazard associated with materials containing mixtures of primordial radionuclides. It enables comparison of the radiological effects of different radionuclide concentrations in a uniform manner. Ra_{eq} which is measured in Bq kg⁻¹, is based on the premise that 370 Bq kg⁻¹ of ²²⁶Ra or 259 Bq kg⁻¹ of ²³²Th or 4810 Bq kg⁻¹ of ⁴⁰K each yield an equivalent gamma dose rate (Agbalagba & Onoja, 2011). According to UNSCEAR (2000), the radium equivalent activity is calculated using the following expression:

$$Ra_{eq} \text{ (Bq kg}^{-1}\text{)} = A_{Ra} + 1.43A_{Th} + 0.077A_{K} \quad (3)$$

where A_{Ra}, A_{Th} and A_K are the respective specific activities of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K.

2.3.2 Absorbed dose rate (DR)

In air at 1 meter above the ground surface is a key parameter for assessing external exposure due to gamma radiation from terrestrial radionuclides such as ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K present in soil samples. The dose rate, expressed in nanograys per hour (nGy h⁻¹), was calculated using the formula provided by UNSCEAR (2000):

$$DR \text{ (nGy h}^{-1}\text{)} = 0.461A_{Ra} + 0.623A_{Th} + 0.0414A_{K} \quad (4)$$

where A_{Ra}, A_{Th} and A_K represent the activity concentrations (in Bq/kg) of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K respectively, and the coefficients (0.461, 0.623 and 0.014) are dose conversion factors corresponding to each radionuclide

2.3.3 Annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE)

Estimates the radiation dose received by individuals due to outdoor gamma exposure, and is expressed in millisieverts per year (mSv y⁻¹). It was computed using the following relationship (Samafou *et al.*, 2023; UNSCEAR, 2000):

$$AEDE \text{ (mSv y}^{-1}\text{)} = DR \text{ (nGy h}^{-1}\text{)} \times 8760 \text{ (hr y}^{-1}\text{)} \times 0.7 \text{ (Sv Gy}^{-1}\text{)} \times 0.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (mSv y}^{-1}\text{)} \quad (5)$$

where 0.7 Sv Gy⁻¹ is the dose conversion coefficient from absorbed dose in air to effective dose, and 0.2 is the outdoor occupancy factor.

2.3.4 Annual gonadal dose equivalent (AGDE)

Annual gonadal dose equivalent (AGDE) assesses the dose received by sensitive human organs such as reproductive organs due to the specific activities of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K in the studied soil samples was calculated using the following formula (Chandrasekaran *et al.*, 2014; Ravisankar *et al.*, 2014):

$$\text{AGDE } (\mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}) = 3.09A_{\text{Ra}} + 4.18A_{\text{Th}} + 0.314A_{\text{K}} \quad (6)$$

2.3.5 Activity utilization index (AUI)

The activity utilization index (AUI) evaluates the potential radiological impact of gamma dose rates resulting from various combinations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in the soil. By applying the proper conversion factors along with the activity concentrations of the particular radionuclides, AUI was computed from the equation (Ravisankar *et al.*, 2014):

$$\text{AUI} = \left(\frac{A_{\text{Ra}}}{50\text{Bq/kg}} \right) f_U + \left(\frac{A_{\text{Th}}}{50\text{Bq/kg}} \right) f_{\text{Th}} + \left(\frac{A_{\text{K}}}{500\text{Bq/kg}} \right) f_{\text{K}} \quad (7)$$

where A_{Ra} , A_{Th} and A_{K} are the measured activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K respectively and f_{K} (0.041), f_{Th} (0.604) and f_U (0.462) are the respective fractional dose contributions from the actual activities of these radionuclides to the overall gamma radiation dose rate in air (Chandrasekaran *et al.*, 2014). Typical reference activity values are 50 Bq/kg for ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th , and 500 Bq/kg for ^{40}K (NEA-OECD, 1979).

2.3.6 Hazard indices (H_{ex} and H_{in})

The external hazard index was used to quantify the radiation risk resulting from external exposure to gamma rays from the soil samples under study (H_{ex}) given by UNSCEAR (2000):

$$H_{\text{ex}} = \frac{A_{\text{Ra}}}{370} + \frac{A_{\text{Th}}}{259} + \frac{A_{\text{K}}}{4810} \quad (8)$$

Similarly, radon and its short-lived daughter radionuclides provide a risk of radiation exposure to respiratory organs. Using the internal hazard index (H_{in}), the internal exposure was measured given by UNSCEAR (2000):

$$H_{\text{in}} = \frac{A_{\text{Ra}}}{185} + \frac{A_{\text{Th}}}{259} + \frac{A_{\text{K}}}{4810} \quad (9)$$

where A_{Ra} , A_{Th} , and A_{K} are the specific activities of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K respectively.

In order for the radiation hazard to be deemed insignificant, the above index value must be less than unity (UNSCEAR, 2000).

2.3.7 Representative gamma index (I_{gr})

The representative gamma index (I_{gr}) is a screening parameter for materials that may pose potential radiation-related health hazards. It was estimated using the relationship (NEA-OECD, 1979; Ravisankar *et al.*, 2014):

$$I_{\text{gr}} = \frac{A_{\text{Ra}}}{150} + \frac{A_{\text{Th}}}{100} + \frac{A_{\text{K}}}{1500} \quad (10)$$

where A_{Ra} , A_{Th} and A_{K} are the specific activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K respectively in Bq kg^{-1} .

2.3.8 Excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR)

Following the assessment of the annual effective dose equivalent, the excess life-time cancer risk (ELCR) was calculated using the corresponding equation (Biere *et al.*, 2025; Ravisankar *et al.*, 2014; Taskin *et al.*, 2009):

$$\text{ELCR} = \text{AEDE} \times \text{DL} \times \text{RF} \quad (11)$$

Where, AEDE denotes the Annual Effective Dose Equivalent, DL represent duration of life, assumed to be (70 years) and RF risk factor, which is taken as (0.05Sv^{-1}) . Ravisankar *et al.* (2014) defined the risk factor as the probability of developing fatal cancer per unit radiation dose, measured in Sieverts, which according to Taskin *et al.* (2009), ICRP 60 assigns a value of 0.05 to the risk factor for the general public in relation to stochastic effects.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Activity Concentrations

Table 2 presents the average activity concentrations (in Bq kg⁻¹) of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in soil samples collected from various locations across the Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic (WUFP) campus in Birnin Kebbi. The measured activity concentrations of ²²⁶Ra ranged from 8.39 ± 0.76 to 26.49 ± 2.09 Bq kg⁻¹, while ²³²Th values varied between 4.61 ± 0.34 and 17.88 ± 0.73 Bq kg⁻¹ across the campus. In contrast, ⁴⁰K exhibited significantly higher activity concentrations, with values ranging from 312.48 ± 8.08 to 488.58 ± 12.72 Bq kg⁻¹.

The overall mean activity concentration for the entire study area for ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K as seen in table 2 were 14.97±0.98, 9.65±0.76 and 393.57±10.19 Bq kg⁻¹ respectively. These values were found to be lower than their respective world average values of 35, 30 and 400 Bq kg⁻¹ published in UNSCEAR (2000) report. Soil contamination status of any given environment by radionuclides is expressed by activity ratios. Calculated cumulative average activity ratios for ²³²Th/²²⁶Ra, ²²⁶Ra/⁴⁰K and ²³²Th/⁴⁰K were 0.64, 0.04 and 0.02 respectively.

Table 2 Sample site and mean radionuclide concentration (Bq kg⁻¹) of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K in soil samples

Sample ID	No of Samples	²²⁶ Ra	²³² Th	⁴⁰ K	Ra _{eq}
ASS	5	17.74±1.13	11.04±0.85	479.71±10.24	70.46±3.13
SVY	4	15.96±1.04	10.46±1.20	448.86±11.82	65.49±3.67
BSD	4	14.00±0.99	9.62±0.90	403.71±16.17	58.83±3.52
LBS	5	17.13±1.09	10.48±1.75	445.81±13.32	66.44±4.62
FLH	4	20.56±1.19	11.01±0.89	415.94±12.13	68.33±3.40
EST	4	14.123±0.90	11.96±0.93	344.76±9.66	57.77±2.97
ADB	5	16.21±1.01	9.61±0.84	397.88±7.66	60.59±2.80
QTS	4	12.62±1.01	8.34±0.79	380.19±7.58	53.82±2.71
STA	5	16.29±1.17	8.37±0.66	403.19±11.67	59.29±3.01
STQ	4	15.04±1.04	8.28±0.69	438.12±10.03	60.61±2.79
ARC	5	13.01±0.97	17.88±0.73	369.54±9.76	67.03±2.76
NCE	5	14.09±1.03	7.96±0.75	331.30±9.03	50.99±2.79
ENG	5	10.51±0.85	6.60±0.68	344.29±8.33	46.46±2.46
MSQ	5	8.39±0.76	14.31±0.68	324.26±9.96	53.83±2.50
CPT	5	9.69±0.84	7.35±0.72	388.23±8.41	50.09±2.52
MLH	5	11.17±0.88	7.50±0.75	461.08±10.35	57.40±2.74
URP	5	16.95±0.61	4.61±0.34	376.52±9.14	52.53±1.80
BLD	5	26.49±2.09	5.15±0.36	312.48±8.08	57.91±3.22
ACC	5	12.84±0.54	16.86±0.29	325.18±7.89	61.99±1.56
CLC	5	15.60±0.70	7.95±0.61	401.38±10.04	57.88±2.34
ICT	5	16.48±0.67	7.68±0.67	486.58±12.72	64.92±2.60
Min		8.39±0.76	4.61±0.34	312.48±8.08	46.46±2.46
Max		26.49±2.09	17.88±0.73	486.58±12.72	70.46±3.13
Mean		14.97±0.98	9.65±0.76	393.57±10.19	59.08±2.85

The calculated activity ratios were found to be less than unity, which indicates that the distribution of primordial radionuclides across the campus remains within the bounds of natural background radiation levels. These ratios confirm the absence of any significant radioactive contamination from anthropogenic sources. A graphical representation of the computed activity ratios is presented in Figure 1

The Radium equivalent activity (Ra_{eq}), which offers a single index to represent the combined radioactivity due to ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K , was also evaluated to better understand the radiological impact. Ra_{eq} values for the soil samples ranged from $46.46 \pm 2.46 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ to $70.46 \pm 3.13 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$, with a cumulative mean of $59.08 \pm 2.85 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$, as shown in column 7 of Table 2.

These values are well below the recommended safety limit of 370 Bq kg^{-1} established by UNSCEAR (2000), suggesting that the external gamma dose rate is not expected to exceed 1.5 mGy per year, and thus does not pose a significant radiological hazard to individuals within the study area.

Figure 1. Activity ratios $^{232}Th/^{226}Ra$, $^{226}Ra/^{40}K$, and $^{232}Th/^{40}K$ for the soil samples

3.2 Radiation Hazard Parameters

Various radiological parameters were derived from the activity concentration of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K using appropriate mathematical models. The results of these computations are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Radiation dose and radiological hazard indices of soil samples from Polytechnic

Sample ID	No of Samples	DR (nGy h ⁻¹)	AEDE (mSv y ⁻¹)	AGDE (μSvy ⁻¹)	AUI = 1	Hex ≤ 1	Hin ≤ 1	I _{yr} ≤ 1	ELCR (x10 ⁻³)
ASS	5	34.86	0.04	251.57	0.34	0.19	0.24	0.55	0.15
SVY	4	32.41	0.04	234.00	0.31	0.18	0.22	0.51	0.14
BSD	4	29.11	0.04	210.21	0.28	0.16	0.20	0.46	0.12
LBS	5	32.83	0.04	236.72	0.32	0.18	0.23	0.52	0.14
FLH	4	33.49	0.04	240.16	0.36	0.18	0.24	0.52	0.14
EST	4	28.13	0.03	201.89	0.30	0.16	0.19	0.44	0.12
ADB	5	29.89	0.04	215.20	0.30	0.16	0.21	0.47	0.13
QTS	4	26.72	0.03	193.22	0.25	0.15	0.18	0.42	0.11
STA	5	29.39	0.04	211.89	0.28	0.16	0.20	0.46	0.13
STQ	4	30.22	0.04	218.64	0.27	0.16	0.20	0.48	0.13
ARC	5	32.22	0.04	230.96	0.37	0.18	0.22	0.51	0.14
NCE	5	25.13	0.03	180.85	0.25	0.14	0.18	0.39	0.11
ENG	5	23.20	0.03	168.17	0.20	0.13	0.15	0.37	0.10
MSQ	5	26.04	0.03	187.58	0.28	0.15	0.17	0.42	0.11
CPT	5	25.10	0.03	182.56	0.21	0.14	0.16	0.40	0.11
HS	5	28.92	0.04	210.65	0.23	0.16	0.19	0.46	0.12
URP	5	26.31	0.03	189.86	0.24	0.14	0.19	0.41	0.11
BLD	5	28.37	0.03	201.47	0.33	0.16	0.23	0.44	0.12
ACC	5	29.67	0.04	212.25	0.35	0.17	0.20	0.47	0.13
CL	5	28.75	0.04	207.47	0.27	0.16	0.20	0.45	0.12
ICT	5	32.54	0.04	235.79	0.28	0.18	0.22	0.51	0.14
Min		23.20	0.03	168.17	0.20	0.13	0.15	0.37	0.10
Max		34.86	0.04	251.57	0.37	0.19	0.24	0.55	0.15
Mean		29.21	0.04	210.53	0.29	0.16	0.20	0.46	0.13

The mean gamma absorbed dose rate (DR) in air at a height of 1 meter above ground level across the Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic (WUP) campus ranged from 23.20 to 34.86 nGy h⁻¹, with a cumulative average of 29.21 nGy h⁻¹. The corresponding annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE) recorded a cumulative mean value of 0.04 mSv y⁻¹. Both values fall below the global averages of 57 nGy h⁻¹ for absorbed dose rate and 0.07 mSv y⁻¹ for annual effective dose, as reported by UNSCEAR (2000), indicating low external radiation exposure across the study area.

Further radiological assessment revealed cumulative values for the activity utilization index (AUI) and the gamma radiation index (I_{γr}) to be 0.29 and 0.46, respectively, as shown in Table 3. These values are significantly below the threshold limit of 1, which is the recommended upper limit for safe exposure according to UNSCEAR guidelines, confirming the absence of significant radiological health risks from soil exposure on campus.

Comparative evaluation of the external hazard index (H_{ex}) and the internal hazard index (H_{in}) computed for the entire WUPF campus is shown in figure 2. The average values for H_{ex} and H_{in} were 0.16 and 0.20 respectively, which are below the safety limit of unity, UNSCEAR (2000).

Figure 2 H_{ex} and H_{in} of soil samples from WUFP Campus

Excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR) which gives an indication of the likelihood of any cancer incidence occurring among the population in WUFP campus was plotted and shown in figure 3. Cumulative ELCR average was determined to be 0.13×10^{-3} , which is lower than the global average value of 0.29×10^{-3} reported by UNSCEAR (2000), and also falls below the low-level radiation threshold of 0.05 established by the International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP).

Figure 3 ELCR of soil samples from WUFP Campus

Generally, results of this investigation shows that the radiation threat to the general public due to exposure to natural radionuclides in the soil of WUFP campus is insignificant. Furthermore, the likelihood of any cancer incidence among the population of WUFP campus is negligible.

3.3 Statistical Analysis

Results of activity concentrations of primordial radionuclides in soil samples from WUFP campus, together with the corresponding computed radiological hazard parameters were analyzed statistically using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 26. Results of the analysis demonstrated that the distribution of radionuclide concentrations adhered to a normal distribution pattern, as confirmed by the Anderson-Darling normality test, with p-values ≥ 0.05 , indicating no significant deviation from normality. The frequency distribution histograms depicting these patterns are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Frequency distribution histogram of (a) ^{226}Ra , (b) ^{232}Th and (c) ^{40}K in Soil of WUFP Campus

3.4 Pearson's correlation analysis

Table 4 present the linear Pearson correlation coefficient among the radiological parameters of soils within the WUFP campus, determined using Pearson's correlation analysis at a significance of $p < 0.05$.

Table 4 correlation coefficients between radiological parameters for soil of WUFP Campus

	²²⁶ Ra	²³² Th	⁴⁰ K	Ra _{eq}	DR	AEDE	AGDE	AUI	H _{ex}	H _{in}	I _{yr}	ELCR
²²⁶ Ra	1.00											
²³² Th	-0.23	1.00										
⁴⁰ K	0.13	-0.14	1.00									
Ra _{eq}	0.53	0.47	0.58	1.00								
DR	0.53	0.39	0.67	0.99	1.00							
AEDE	0.49	0.30	0.51	0.82	0.82	1.00						
AGDE	0.50	0.37	0.70	0.99	1.00	0.82	1.00					
AUI	0.60	0.63	0.08	0.85	0.79	0.68	0.76	1.00				
H _{ex}	0.53	0.47	0.57	0.99	0.98	0.83	0.98	0.85	1.00			
H _{in}	0.79	0.22	0.48	0.93	0.93	0.79	0.91	0.84	0.92	1.00		
I _{yr}	0.48	0.44	0.66	0.99	1.00	0.81	1.00	0.79	0.98	0.91	1.00	
ELCR	0.49	0.40	0.66	0.98	0.98	0.80	0.98	0.77	0.97	0.90	0.98	1.00

Very poor relationships were noticed between ²²⁶Ra and ²³²Th ($r = -0.23$), ²²⁶Ra and ⁴⁰K ($r = +0.13$), and ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K ($r = -0.14$). This shows that the primordial radionuclides may have different origins within the soil samples. Furthermore, ⁴⁰K showed strong positive correlation with DR ($r = +0.67$), and with AGDE ($r = +0.70$), indicating that ⁴⁰K is the main contributor to the gamma radiation and the annual gonadal exposure measured within the campus. Additionally, a very strong correlation was found between with ²²⁶Ra ($r = +0.79$) and the internal hazard index H_{in} as seen in tale 4, which indicates that ²²⁶Ra is principally responsible for internal exposure to gamma radiation among the population.

4.0 CONCLUSION

Activity concentrations of primordial radionuclides in soil samples from Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic, Birnin-kebbi campus were measured using a thallium doped sodium iodide NaI(Tl) gamma detector. Key radiological hazard indices were calculated based on the measured activity levels. The cumulative average activity concentrations for ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K were 14.99 ± 0.98 , 9.67 ± 0.76 , and 394.24 ± 10.19 Bq kg⁻¹ respectively, all below international safety thresholds established by UNSCEAR. The mean absorbed dose rate (DR) across the campus was 29.21 nGy h⁻¹, with a corresponding annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE) of 0.04 mSv y⁻¹, both of which fall below global average values. The excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR) was estimated at 0.13×10^{-3} , which is also below the recommended limit of 0.29×10^{-3} , indicating that the likelihood of any cancer incidence occurring among the students of the campus and the entire work force is negligible. Although the results of this investigation does not show any radiological threat to the public, continuous monitoring of the environment from the perspective of radiation protection is encouraged.

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